

A Study of English Creative Writing Skills and Academic Performance of C.B.S.E. and State Board School Children

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1.0 Introduction

Presently, there is great demand in India as well as many countries of human resources proficient in the English language. Moreover, the younger generation in India is convinced that English language will give them more opportunities for economic and career advancement. English has changed from the language of the west to language of the modern era. English today is India's most important language of knowledge – one that empowers students to be not just consumers of knowledge but, more importantly, participants in the production of knowledge. However, the use of knowledge appears to be guided by the amount of creativity one has in the presentation of concepts, facts or other aspects of life.

1.1 Creative Writing

Creative writing is the process of inventing or rather presenting one's thoughts in an appealing way. Here, the writer thinks critically and reshapes something known into something that is different and original. Moreover, each piece of writing has a purpose and is targeted at an audience and is organized cohesively with a clear beginning, middle and an end. Also, attention is paid to choice of apt vocabulary, figurative use of language and style. Thus, creative writing is any writing that goes outside the bounds of normal professional, journalistic, academic, or technical forms of literature, typically identified by an emphasis on narrative craft, character development, and the use of literary tropes.

Creative Writing is a subjective creation of a picture of the world. It is an expression of the realization of the joys and sorrows, as well as a way to let one's imagination run wild. Creativity is multidimensional. It can be a trait, skill, ability, or an approach, or all of these. It has been stated that the best way to help students discover their colourful world with the help of their senses, by creating a rainbow in the class. To achieve this one must realise that creativity and education go hand in hand. Self-expression, curiosity, exploration and experimentation, imagination, open-ended thinking, all the natural elements in creativity are important in a child's development.

Today, most children are exposed to creative writing in the early grades of elementary school. Children begin to think about words and become curious about creating their own stories when they are made by their parents and teachers. With Simple drawings and inventive spelling, even very young children begin to weave their own tales of fun, adventure, mystery, and magic, and this skill grows as they learn to read more types of literature and explore different kinds of writing. The idea of creativity in Children's writing relates to their school experiences and required state standardized assessments, and also reveals its connection with brain dominance. In the light of above information researcher made an attempt to explore the relationship between English language creative writing skill and academic performance of the students learning in CBSE and Maharashtra State Board Schools.

2.0 Research Methodology

2.1 Study Area – Nagpur

The study area for this investigation was Nagpur City. The CBSE and State Board Schools of Nagpur City were selected for the purpose of data collection.

2.2 Research Design, Sample Selection and Sample Size

The design of the study was random group design, where the students from CBSE and State Board Schools are selected randomly. In all total 500 students (250 each from CBSE and State Board Schools of Nagpur City) were selected

2.3 Data Collection

Data for this study was collected using survey methodology. The primary data collection in view of the objectives of the study involved preparation of research instrument (questionnaire). The process of developing the research instrument is based on generally accepted principles of instrument design, and is carried out according to the standard methodology. The researcher herself performed a pilot study on the students of CBSE and State Board Schools of Nagpur District. All the test items were applied on a small group and the problems faced during testing, were identified and rectified following standard procedures.

2.4 Statistical Analysis of Data

The data generated during the study is processed using various statistical tests with the aid of SPSS 18.0 statistical software. The data characteristics (descriptive statistics), frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, etc. were determined. The inferential statistics like correlation coefficient was used. The accepted significance level was 0.05.

3.0 Results of the Study

3.1 Assessment of creative writing skills of students of CBSE and State Board Schools

Table 1: Assessment of creative writing skills of children studying in Standard IV of schools affiliated to CBSE and State Board

Factors	School	N	Mean	±SD	Min	Max	Std. Score	% Achievement
Content	CBSE	30	7.7	±1.4	4.0	9.0	10	77.0
	SB	30	6.3	±1.4	5.0	9.0	10	73.0
Fluency	CBSE	30	7.4	±1.7	4.0	9.5	10	74.0
	SB	30	8.0	±1.0	7.0	9.5	10	80.0
Accuracy	CBSE	30	7.2	±1.6	5.0	9.0	10	72.0
	SB	30	6.1	±0.8	6.0	8.0	10	61.0
Expression & Language	CBSE	30	8.5	±1.0	6.0	9.5	10	85.0
	SB	30	6.8	±1.0	5.5	9.0	10	68.0
Creativity	CBSE	30	8.1	±1.3	4.0	9.0	10	81.0
	SB	30	6.6	±0.9	6.0	8.5	10	66.0

Interpretation of creative writing ability: < 5=Poor; 5-6: Average; 7-8: Good; >8=Excellent

Above **Table 1** presents results pertaining to assessment of creative writing skills of children studying in standard IV of the schools affiliated to CBSE and State Board. The results are as follows

- *Content:* The study results show that the scores of CBSE and state board students with respect to content of the matter are 7.7 ± 1.4 and 6.3 ± 1.4 respectively.
- *Fluency:* The scores with respect to fluency aspect of the writing indicated 7.4 ± 1.7 (for CBSE students) and 8.0 ± 1.0 (State board students).

- *Accuracy*: The study results show that the scores of CBSE and state board students with respect to accuracy aspect are 7.2 ± 1.4 and 6.1 ± 1.4 respectively.
- *Expression and Language*: The study results show that the scores of CBSE and state board students with respect to expression and language of the matter are 8.5 ± 1.0 and 6.8 ± 1.0 respectively.
- *Creativity*: The study results show that the scores of CBSE and state board students with respect to creativity in the write up are 8.1 ± 1.3 and 6.6 ± 0.9 respectively.

3.2 Creative writing ability of students of class IV

Table 2: Assessment of creative writing ability Standard IV students of schools affiliated to CBSE and State Board

Factors	School	N	Mean	\pm SD	Min	Max	Std. Score	% Achievement
Total Score of Creative Writing Test	CBSE	30	37.5	± 5.9	23.0	44.0	50	75.0
	SB	30	34.8	± 3.5	30.5	42.5	50	69.6

Interpretation of creative writing ability: < 25=Poor; 25-35: Average; 35-45: Good; >45=Excellent

Above **Table 2** presents results pertaining to creative writing skills of children of standard IV and studying in schools affiliated to CBSE and State Board. Based on the data, it is evident that CBSE students have an average score of 37.5 ± 5.9 (indicative of average creative writing skill) in creative writing test, while those belonging to state board schools, it was 37.8 ± 3.5 (indicating good creative writing skill).

3.3 Academic performance of students of class IV

Table 3: Assessment of academic performance of children studying in Standard IV of schools affiliated to CBSE and State Board

Average Grades during	School	Mean	\pm SD	Min	Max	Std. Score	% Achievement
2012	CBSE	71.4	± 9.5	53.6	82.3	100	71.4
	SB	66.8	± 9.8	54.3	83.6	100	66.8
2013	CBSE	72.2	± 8.6	58.5	85.6	100	72.2
	SB	66.7	± 8.7	53.6	85.6	100	66.7

Above **Table 3** presents results pertaining to academic performance of the children studying in standard IV of the schools affiliated to CBSE and State Board. Based on the data, it is evident that in the academic year of 2012 CBSE students had a mean percentage score of 71.4 ± 9.5 and state board students had a mean score of 66.8 ± 9.8 . In addition to it, in the year 2013, CBSE students had a mean average score of 72.2 ± 8.6 and state board students had a mean score of 66.7 ± 8.7 . Overall, it appears that in general the student's performance on the academic front is of moderate nature.

3.4 Relationship between creative writing skills and academic performance

Table 4: Correlation between various aspects of creativity and Standard IV student's grades

School	Creative writing related factors	Correlation coefficient (r^2) Student's grade
CBSE	Content	.761**
	Fluency	.551**

	Accuracy	.839**
	Expression and Language	.637**
	Creativity	.778**
	Total - Creativity Score	.853**
State Board	Content	.118
	Fluency	.660**
	Accuracy	.752**
	Expression and Language	.071
	Creativity	.593**
	Total - Creativity Score	.590**

** : Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

* : Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Above **Table 4** presents results regarding the correlations between various aspects of the creative writing related aspects and the student's academic grades. The results of the correlation coefficient analysis is as follows

- *CBSE Students*: The data showed that there is positive relationship between various creative writing related skills and the overall academic grades (of year 2012) of students of class IV. Specifically, the accuracy ($r^2=0.839$, $p<0.01$) and creativity ($r^2=0.778$, $p<0.01$) of the write up has strong positive relationship with the academic grades.
- *State Board Students*: The data showed that there is positive relationship between different creative writing related skills and the overall academic grades (of year 2012) of students of class IV. Specifically, the accuracy ($r^2=0.752$, $p<0.01$) and fluency ($r^2=0.660$, $p<0.01$) of the write up has strong positive relationship with the academic grades.

4.0 Conclusions

4.1 Creative writing skills of students of CBSE and State Board Schools - Class IV

- Based on the study results, it is evident that the ability of students (of class IV) from CBSE schools vis-à-vis content, accuracy, expression and language was better than that observed in the students of State Board Schools. However, there was no significant difference in the writing fluency of students of both the schools. Overall, the creativity of students from CBSE schools was noticeably better than those studying in State Board Schools.

4.2 Academic performance of students of class IV

- Based on the study results, it is concluded that consistently, the academic performance of the students from CBSE schools is better than those studying in State Board schools.

4.3 Creative writing ability of students of class IV

- In view of the study results pertaining to creative writing skills (keep consistency) of children of standard IV, it is evident that there is difference in the creative writing skills of the students of CBSE and State Board schools. How does it differ from 1st bullet above?

4.4 Correlation between various aspects of creativity and student's grades

- *CBSE Students*: There is significant positive relationship between various creative writing related skills and the overall academic grades of students of class IV. Specifically, the accuracy and creativity of write up has strong positive relationship with the academic grades.

- *State Board Students*: There is positive relationship between different creative writing related skills and the overall academic grades of students of class IV. Specifically, the accuracy and fluency of the write up has strong positive relationship with the academic grades.

5.0 Bibliography

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